

Career Development Plan

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BRIEF OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH PROJECT AND MAJOR ACCOMPLISHMENTS

EXPECTED:

The research project **PANICOCENE** seeks to contribute to filling a persistent gap in research on framing and narratives of climate change-induced mobilities (CCIM). It aims to investigate how the US and Italian printed and online news media have framed CCIM over the past 20 years, which is identified as a crucial timeframe during which discourses and narratives on CCIM have significantly intensified and changed, and to understand if and how news media and activists rely on researches in CCIM. All too often, the images conjured are of inevitable, massive, and permanent cross-border movements, contributing to apocalyptic and securitized climate imaginaries that cast mobilities as a threat to Western societies. **The overall goals** of PANICOCENE are to identify and analyze the ways by which news media may lead to stereotyping CCIM, thus impacting on perceptions of readerships, general audiences and ultimately policy-making, and to propose a space for collaboration between activists, journalists and academics. Using 'mobility justice' as an analytical lens, PANICOCENE would like to move beyond alarming and uncertain narratives on CCIM, which might increase 'uncertainty' in public understanding of the issue, and to find new and alternative ways to frame it and to disseminate research outside the academia in media debates.

LONG-TERM CAREER OBJECTIVES (over 5 years):

1. Goals:

This project will allow me to complement and complete my postdoctoral career within the specific fields of media and socio-cultural communication, mobilities and migration, sociology and environmental studies. The Marie Curie fellowship will propel my research skills and capabilities to the desired level of **professional maturity** and allow me to be **recognised at an international level**. The acquisition of new and powerful methodological approaches will allow me to develop my competence in two distinct but complementary ways.

Firstly, in terms of **academic production**, the fellowship will give me the opportunity to disseminate my research through the publication of peer-reviewed journal paper and a monograph; this output will enable me to **enrich my track record** and thus acquire more credibility and opportunities in my academic field.

Secondly, envisioning an interdisciplinary diversification of my expertise in the theoretical, methodological and professional areas, the research project will hence foster my professional maturity, providing me with the essential means to stabilise and internationalise my professional position and possibly going further. Thanks to this **network, training, transferable competencies, management and scientific skills** acquired during the GF, the groundwork will be laid for the development of a follow-on project examining framing and narratives of climate mobilities to be submitted in the framework of the **ERC starting grants**. The GF will create a bridge between UNIBO, Columbia and Durham, enhancing both the range of their international activities and the interdisciplinary collaboration between research groups.

Moreover, this GF will help me develop skills for **working in careers beyond academia**. PANICOENE will increase my potential to work and collaborate with non-academic entities. During the placement, the collaboration with the association Carta di Roma will allow me to acquire skills highly valued by employers. Further, the international experiences, the training in Critical Discourse Analysis and complementary skills, dissemination activities, teaching experience, and the expertise acquired in sociology and media communication, together with publications arising from PANICOENE, will increase my chance of success in obtaining the **National Scientific Qualification (ASN)** in Italy as both, before **associate professor**, and after **full professor** in **Sociology of Culture and Communication (SPS/08)** and will significantly increase my potential to compete for a position at world class Universities.

2. What further research activity or other training is needed to attain these goals?

- Further training regarding the preparation of **advanced research proposals** to obtain funding for future academic/research career progression (**European Research Council (ERC)**, National Science and Research Councils is needed; together with **training on project management**, financial aspects in project management, innovation, entrepreneurship, finance and leadership);
- Increasing **publication record** (more peer reviewed journal papers published, as well as indexed conference papers and book chapters);
- Mentoring activities have to be improved through **teaching and supervising experience** (present lectures, supervise Master and PhD thesis, obtain formal teaching accreditation);
- Strengthening **professional network, communication and dissemination tasks**, and participate in extra academic activities (such as organization of conferences, participation in peer reviewing and editorial tasks, involvement with research groups and specialized research committees);

SHORT-TERM OBJECTIVES (1-2 years):

Publications in major peer-review journals, chapters of edited books, and conferences presentations and/or proceedings are expected based on the progress of my research and the specific results obtained.

1. Research results

- o **Anticipated publications:**
 - **Peer-reviewed journal papers:**
 - Giacomelli, E., Walker S. Encountering mobility (in)justice through the lived experiences of Senegalese fishing communities. *Mobilities*.
 - Giacomelli, E., Cappi V. *Information campaigns and climate mobilities*
 - Giacomelli E., Cappi V. *Italian climate diaries: narratives of the climate crisis*
 - Giacomelli, E., *Activism, Media and Academica: how to collaborate in climate change-induced mobilities?*
 - Giacomelli E., *Panicocene, the age of panic: a discussion on media narratives of climate change and migration*.

- A peer-reviewed journal paper on comparison of case studies (Italy - US) on framing and narratives of the climate crisis and mobilities nexus submitted, for example, to Global Media and Communication;
- A book chapter in English discussing state-of-art of framing and narratives of climate change induced-mobilities;
- **Monography:** Giacomelli, E., Musarò P. *Climate and mobility justice: how to deal with the Panicocene*, Palgrave.
 - o **Anticipated Conference, Workshop attendance courses, Summer Schools and/or paper and seminar presentation:**
 - World Refugee Day, June 20;
 - Conference of the Italian Sociological Association - Cultural Processes and Institutions;
 - IMISCOE Conference - IMISCOE is the most important research network regarding migration and mobilities and I think it is quite important to include PANICOECENE in such event;
 - Conference of the Environmental & Climate Mobilities Network, hosted in 2024 by the Hugo Observatory/University of Liège, on the topic of Environmental Changes and Migration: Bridging Disciplines for a New Research Agenda. This is a transdisciplinary network connecting people working on migration and human im/mobility in the context of environmental and climate change and I am really excited in connecting with such network:
 - "Re-think the challenge Conference" in Bologna, with artists and activists working on climate change and migration. I am planning to engage with a broader public beyond academics, as I foreseen in PANICOECENE:
 - European Sociological Association Conference;
 - Researchers' Night Participation in the European Researchers Night at UNIBO;
 - Organisation of seminars at UNIBO, Columbia and Durham in agreement with supervisors on research themes;
 - International School on Climate Migration at SOAS;
 - Climate Diaries Workshops;
 - Lecture in the Climate Justice University;
 - Seminar in the World Congress of Climate Justice;
 - Paper presentation at the Conference of the Italian Sociology Association;
 - Paper presentation at the Conference of the Italian Scientific Society of Sociology, Culture, Communication.

2. Research Skills and techniques:

Working across disciplinary boundaries, including media and socio-cultural communication, mobilities and migration, sociology and environmental studies, is important for furthering knowledge and reciprocal awareness and will enhance the dynamism of the research. The research will adopt an **action research methodology** upholding the belief that it is important to conduct research 'by, with and for people, rather than research on people'¹. Action research has been defined as 'the study of a social situation with a view to improving the quality of action within it'².

In CIESIN (Columbia University), a mutually enriching convergence of social studies with environmental concerns, together with the importance given to information and communication aspects in academic settings and beyond, perfectly matches my research interests and offers a most congenial intellectual environment to conduct the proposed research project. During the outgoing phase, by having the possibility of access to important

¹ Reason, P., & McArdle, K.L. (2004). Brief notes on the practice of action research. Centre for Action Research in Professional Practice, p.1.

² Elliott, J. (1991). Action Research for Educational Change, Milton Keynes: Open University Press, p. 69.

primary and secondary sources available at Columbia University and close collaboration with the Society of Environmental Journalists, I will acquire new expertise in **data capture and analytical skills** of intersectional and interdisciplinary lens of research.

Moreover, I require additional training in framing and narratives, as well as exposure to **diverse methodologies and perspectives**. I will benefit University of Bologna's expertise on **qualitative methodological approaches**, particularly Critical Discourse Analysis and Content Analysis.

For developing new research skills in a diverse research environment through exposure to the non-academic sector, through the placement period at Carta di Roma, an association founded in December 2011 with the goal of implementing the Journalist's Code of Conduct on immigration, signed by the National Council of Journalists and the National Federation of the Italian Press, which seeks to be a stable reference point for those who work on a daily basis with media and minority issues, I will be working closely with media specialists and develop **original, independent and critical thinking, specifically in migration and mobilities discourses**. Finally, during the placement, the collaboration with association Carta di Roma will allow me to acquire **skills highly valued by employers**.

3. Research management:

Thanks to network, trainings, transferable competences, management and scientific skills acquired during PANICOCENE, the groundwork will be laid for the development of a follow-on project examining framing and narratives climate mobilities to be submitted in the framework of the **ERC starting grants**.

4. Communication skills:

The Marie Curie Individual Fellowship constitutes an invaluable opportunity to work on my **personal presentation, research, and communication skills**. Indeed, the international conferences, workshops and seminars that I will plan to attend, according to my career development plan, will be crucial in further developing my research activities and communication skills.

The outcomes of the research project will be communicated by means of several **dissemination initiatives** directed both at **academic communities** and **general audiences**.

Public engagement activities will be conducted in accordance with the University of Bologna. The strategy proposed here includes several ways to create 'popular' awareness principally about one of the main topics of the project – narratives and framing of climate change induced-mobilities and the risk of stereotypical of climate migrants.

On the other hand, as a visiting scholar, I will be expected to contribute to the extant research culture in CIESIN (Columbia University). CIESIN aims to ensure that all academic visitors are fully integrated into it. This would normally include the following activities: delivery of a research seminar paper on the proposed research; attendance at regular research seminars and workshops within the Climate School and other research centres within the University; publish research papers in refereed journals; and attendance at international conferences as speaker. All these activities just listed will help me to improve my **oral and written scientific communication skills**.

5. Other professional training (course work, teaching activity):

Teaching assistantships of undergraduate students, mentoring of younger researchers, and other activities of this kind are considered extremely important and definitely worth trying during the Marie-Curie project.

6. Anticipated networking opportunities:

PANICOCENE will create a bridge between University of Bologna, Columbia University and Durham University, enhancing both the range of their international activities and the interdisciplinary collaboration between research groups. This connection will aid in creating a global network of scholars interested in climate change-induced mobilities.

During my stay at Columbia University as a Marie Curie Research Fellow, I will plan to work in close collaboration with my academic advisor, Dr. Susana Adamo, and the other colleagues of CIESIN. I will also develop the cooperative research network “Reimagining Mobilities” at the University of Bologna. In the secondment, I will collaborate with Andrew Baldwin and his research teams working on climate mobilities.

Further, I will be in direct contact with other networks and colleagues working on climate migration topics, such as the **Environmental and Climate Mobilities Network**³, **Climate Mobility Community Action Network**⁴, the **Climate Mobility Africa Research Network**⁵, and the **Food-Climate-Migration Nexus Network**.

Finally, international conferences and other mobility possibilities allowed by the fellowship (i.e. the anticipated conference presentations, seminars and workshop attendances listed above) will constitute a great opportunity to meet well-known researchers from around the world.

7. Other activities (community, etc) with professional relevance:

I would like to improve my transferable skills, such as teamwork, critical thinking and creativity, in fact I would like to create a podcast on climate mobilities to disseminate and communicate research results in an alternative way.

Date & Signature of fellow:

Date & Signature of supervisor:

27/02/24

28/02/24

³ <https://www.climatemobilities.network/>.

⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7151196091575595010/>.

⁵ <https://www.cmarnetwork.com/>.